

Downey et al. "Hay provision affects 24-h performance of normal and abnormal oral behaviors in individually housed dairy calves"



Supplemental Figure 5. Proportion of time engaged in tongue rolling in wk 2, 4, 6, and 8 averaged by individual calf in 15-min bins over a 24-h d. Each colored line represents a different calf. Dashed lines represent milk feedings, which occurred at 06:45, 12:45, and 18:45 h in wk 2-6 and at 18:45 h in wk 8, during step-down weaning.